

FACTORS FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF INSPECTOR-PSYCHOLOGIST

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Abstract. *This article discusses the research of the manifestation and development of competence factors in the activities of the inspector-psychologist and the improvement of his specific social-psychological factors, the determination of the social-psychological factors and components that develop the inspector-psychologist's social-psychological competence, the inspector-psychologist's communicative, research on the manifestation and development of emotional and personality components; in the development of the social-psychological competence of the inspector-psychologist, their connection with the social-legal system is revealed.*

Researching the psychological aspects of professional and social-psychological competence of employees in the world, research of socio-psychological factors of development of their professional competence, researches are being carried out to evaluate the professional competence of employees, to develop a set of special systematic psychological methods aimed at improving their professional competence, and to prevent crime. The impact of behavioral indicators on the professional activities of employees, their professional competence, in particular, improving the level of psychological preparation for professional activities by the Human Resources Professional Association (HRPA), particularly, to determine the socio-psychological factors and mechanisms of development of their professional competence, increasing the role of professional readiness of employees and determining the issue of their impact on the effectiveness of their activity is gaining urgent importance.

In our republic increasing the efficiency of law enforcement agencies, special attention is being paid to the issues of further improvement of the system of training of inspector-psychologists on issues of minors and raising their level of professional training in recent years. Research on improving the professional competence of the inspector-psychologist on the issues of minors is of great importance in performing the important tasks specified in the legal documents. That's why, to increase the professional competence of inspector-psychologists on minor issues, to realize the characteristic features of their personal qualities, professional which directly affects the effectiveness of their professional activity through psychocorrective and developmental methods, formation of communicative and social-psychological competence factors is defined as an urgent problem.

Keywords: *inspector-psychologist, socio-psychological competence, psychological expertise, professional competence, competence, emotional intelligence, professional activity.*

Many studies have been conducted abroad, especially in Russia and Uzbekistan to study and research the factors of social and psychological competence at a certain level in psychology. Methodological foundations of the problem are revealed in these explorations. The common aspect of these approaches is that most researchers directly connect the issue of social-psychological competence with the process of formation of professional competence. Because, since the person himself is a social being in the literal sense, his professional direction and the manifestation of his

professional ability are directly determined by socio-psychological factors of a certain level. In this sense, each socio-psychological competence factor is important in the professional development of a person.

By the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan improvement of the professional competence of inspectors-psychologists in matters of minors, special attention is being paid to their effective functioning and further reform of the education and training system in recent years. Specially, a number of regulatory and legal documents are being adopted due to the fact that employees have a modern worldview and changes in their thinking, that is, their professional competence.

In our opinion, we can assess the following competences of inspector-psychologists for minor issues as the main basic competences that must be formed in the course of their activity:

- Socially active citizenship;
- Universal;
- Communicative;
- Ability to apply psychodiagnostics in practice;
- Self-development as a person;
- To be aware of the news of one's field;
- Having legal and psychological knowledge.

Based on the above, it is necessary to further develop the following basic competencies of inspector-psychologists on minor issues:

Communicative competence:

In the course of activities with minors, inspector-psychologists can express their attitude within the scope of their authority, based on legal grounds, orally and in writing, using short, reasonable, understandable and effective means of communication, to have the ability to put the accent correctly when expressing their opinions, follow the standards of literary language, and express their opinion without mistakes based on the rules of spelling and etiquette;

being able to listen to the opinions of the team and group members, respect the interlocutors, react correctly to objectionable opinions, and contribute to the formation of their opinion, depending on the situation or circumstances.

Competence of self-development as a person:

to make continuously self-development as a person, striving for spiritual-ethical, psychological and intellectual perfection into a permanent vital-spiritual need;

to respect national and universal values and diligently follow them;

to regularly read and study literature of various directions throughout his life, to draw conclusions and take lessons from systematic analysis, and to be able to use them in work as a proof and proof of their opinion in necessary cases;

to be able to take a critical approach to own actions and opinions, to be able to control self, to be able to respond to the content of oral and written texts.

Competence, as a practical application of sufficient knowledge, skills, competences and life experiences in the relevant field, is of great importance in the life of a juvenile inspector-psychologist, in his professional development, therefore, we consider it appropriate to first of all form and develop the factors of professional competence of inspector-psychologists for minors, as well as to achieve the formation and development of basic (basic) competencies in them.

Based on research on competence, we divided the set of criteria for determining the factors of professional competence of juvenile inspector-psychologists into the following.

Cognitive;

know the special rules for understanding minors in the course of activities with minors;

Social memory - memory aimed at remembering the image of minors, their name;

Social intuition - is the ability to understand the motives of minors' moods, emotions, actions, and the ability to observe behavior in social and psychological content at an appropriate level in communication with minors;

Being able to prognostically assess social reality - form a plan of personal actions, consolidate one's own activities, see personal activities through the eyes of others, and evaluate unused alternative opportunities.

Emtional;

2.1 Social expressiveness - social expressiveness, social sensitivity, social control;

2.2. Empathy is the ability to put oneself in the shoes of other children.

2.3. Self-regulation is the ability to regulate one's emotions and moods.

Moral;

3.1. Social reflection - the skill of listening to minors;

3.2. Social identity - willingness and ability to work in cooperation, ability to interact in a team;

3.3. Social adaptation - the ability to explain and convince others, the ability to get along with others, the manifestation of sincerity in relationships with others.

Now we will go directly to the analysis of the results obtained on the basis of the "Psychodiagnostic test" methodology of V.A. Melnikov, L. Ya. Yampolskiy (Table 1, Figure 1) in determining the socio-psychological characteristics of the manifestation of the professional competence of inspector-psychologists in matters of minors. Today, this psychodiagnostic method is widely used to assess the social and psychological characteristics of many workers. Taking into account the high quality and effectiveness of this method, as well as the importance of socio-psychological competence for the professional competence of the employee, we also decided to use this method in our research work.

Table 1

Indicators of socio-psychological characteristics of the manifestation of professional competence of inspector-psychologists in juvenile matters (according to the method of "Psychodiagnostic test" by V.A. Melnikov, L. Ya. Yampolskiy)

tr	Factors	Indicators	Female employees (n=70)		Male employees (n=190)			
			M ₁	S	M ₂	S		
1	Neuroticism	lower	1,21	4,55	1,90	1,72	4,56	1,31
		medium	4,23		3,87	5,19		2,04
		high	8,21		3,57	7,08		2,18
2	Psychoticism	lower	1,74	4,80	1,38	1,32	5,09	1,45
		medium	4,19		2,60	4,94		1,81
		high	8,46		2,93	9,02		2,23
3	Depression	lower	1,25	4,65	3,56	1,43	5,16	1,29

			medium	4,41		1,86	5,02		2,14
			high	8,28		3,06	9,03		1,16
4	Conscientiousness		lower	1,15	4,77	1,31	1,35	4,80	1,03
		medium	4,76	2,96		5,84	2,64		
		high	8,42	3,29		7,21	1,62		
5	Stagnation		lower	1,34	4,80	1,14	1,37	4,75	1,23
		medium	4,18	2,34		5,15	1,96		
		high	8,89	3,21		7,72	3,08		
6	General activity		lower	1,08	4,54	1,00	1,40	4,75	1,86
		medium	4,41	3,28		5,02	2,05		
		high	8,12	3,11		7,84	1,09		
7	Dependency		lower	1,87	5,10	2,90	1,34	5,13	1,23
		medium	4,51	3,49		5,03	2,03		
		high	8,92	2,92		9,02	1,08		
8	Accessibility		lower	2,21	5,29	3,65	1,97	5,00	2,09
		medium	4,73	3,90		5,02	2,23		
		high	8,93	3,94		8,01	1,78		
9	Aesthetic impression		lower	1,01	5,19	4,03	1,52	5,26	1,06
		medium	5,01	3,45		5,24	3,02		
		high	9,56	3,62		9,01	1,88		
10	Femininity		lower	1,33	3,80	3,58	1,76	3,61	2,12
		medium	3,96	3,11		3,20	2,53		
		high	6,12	1,69		5,88	1,43		

Comment: low (1-2 points), medium (3-6 points), high (7-10 points).

M - Arithmetic mean value. S – Standard deviation

Figure 1. Indicators of socio-psychological characteristics of the manifestation of professional competence of inspector-psychologists on juvenile issues

As can be seen from the above table, the following results were obtained in the research carried out in the exploratory experiment with regard to the ten main factors selected by the methodology:

The overall average score of the female inspector-psychological staff on the neuroticism factor was 4.55 points, but it was lower in 18 of them ($M=1.21$; $S=1.83$), the indicator showed while the overall average score was 4.56 points among male inspector-psychologist employees, 43 showed a lower score ($M=1.21$; $S=1.83$). Employees with a lower index are usually calm and useless, but in some cases (conflicts, inspections) they may have a feeling of anxiety and fear, they doubt their abilities and are characterized by difficulties in the process of work.

According to the factor of psychoticism, the overall average index of female inspector-psychological employees was 4.80 points, of which 19 had a high index ($M=8.46$; $S=2.93$). The overall average score of male inspector-psychologist employees is 5.90 (1.10 points higher than female employees) and 44 of them have a high score ($M=9.03$; $S=2.23$). showed. Such employees represent high tension and excitability. He cares too much about his personal prestige, he painfully accepts criticism and warnings. Egoist is characterized by self-pity and self-reflection.

On the factor of depression, the overall average index of female inspector-psychological employees was 4.65 points, of which 14 employees showed a high index ($M=8.28$; $S=3.06$). The overall average score of male inspector-psychologist employees was 5.16 points, 43 showed a high score ($M=9.03$; $S=1.16$). Despite the fact that such employees are usually diligent, conscientious and responsible, they are very helpless and do not trust themselves in the decisions they make. Their characteristic feature is stubbornness, depression, despondency and dullness. At the same time, they are distinguished by the appearance of alienation and a strong feeling of discomfort.

According to the factor of conscientiousness, the overall average index of female inspector-psychological employees was 4.77 points, and 38 employees showed a low index ($M=1.15$; $S=1.31$). male inspector-psychologist showed a low ($M=1.35$; $S=1.03$) index in 41 employees, while the overall average score was 4.65 points. Such employees usually take everything lightly, carelessly and irresponsibly. They often ignore the fulfillment of their duties and are distinguished by their non-observance of laws and moral norms.

The general average index of female inspector-psychological employees on the stagnation factor was 4.80 points, of which 12 employees showed a high index ($M=8.89$; $S=3.21$). The overall average score of male inspector-psychologist employees was 4.75 points, 61 showed a high score ($M=7.72$; $S=3.08$). Such employees are impulsive and unrestrained, unable or unwilling to restrain themselves, trying to satisfy their desires. Of course, it indicates the possibility of causing various conflict situations in communication with minors, and in difficult situations they will not be able to control themselves.

The overall average score of female inspector-psychological employees on the general activity factor is 4.54 points, of which 11 have a low ($M=1.08$; $S=1.00$) score, the overall average index of male inspector-psychological employees on this factor was 4.75 points, and 41 of them showed a low index ($M=1.40$; $S=1.86$). Employees with a low index are passive, do not take initiative, and do not have enough energy. They are characterized by slowness (speech, movements) and low mobility. They prefer sedentary work and monotonous work. There is no desire for achievements and success. He often avoids additional responsibilities at work, even if he takes responsibility, he puts it on other people's shoulders.

The overall average score of female inspector-psychological employees on the dependency factor is 5.10 points, 12 of them have a higher score ($M=8.92$; $S=2.92$). The overall average index of male inspector-psychological employees was 5.13 points, 34 showed a high index ($M=9.02$; $S=1.08$). Usually such employees are shy and avoid unexpected situations. He feels uncomfortable at unexpected events. He speaks little and is shy in communication, usually does not attract attention and does not interfere in anything. He prefers to have a narrow circle of acquaintances and friends.

On the communication factor, the overall average index of female inspector-psychological employees was 5.29 points, 9 had a low score ($M=2.21$; $S=3.65$), while male the general average index of the inspector-psychologist employees was 5 points, 35 employees showed a low index ($M=1.97$; $S=2.09$). Such employees avoid getting emotionally close to people. Likes solitude, has difficulty communicating with people.

The general average index of female inspector-psychological employees on the factor of aesthetic impressiveness was 5.19 points, of which 13 employees showed a high index ($M=9.56$; $S=3.62$). , the overall average index of male inspector-psychological employees was 5.26 points, 32 of them showed a high index ($M=9.01$; $S=1.88$). Such employees have a rich imagination, strong fantasy, and like sincere feelings. He does not have a sense of responsibility in his actions and does not look at reality and rational perception in his decisions, he trusts his emotions more than logic and considering events.

And finally, the tenth, namely, the overall average index of female inspector-psychological employees on the femininity factor is 3.80 points, of which 11 have a high ($M=6.12$; $S=1.69$) index. showed, the overall average index of male inspector-psychological employees was 3.61 points, 26 of them showed a higher index ($M=5.88$; $S=1.43$). Such employees are sensitive, resistant to grief, gentle, flexible, and simple. They strive to achieve their fantasy and aesthetic goals. Often busy with personal problems, prone to self-analysis and criticism.

The results obtained above showed the need to carry out corrective and developmental measures with them to one degree or another.

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